

Transethosome-mediated curcumin delivery promotes superior wound healing with reduced toxicity

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Abstract

Background: Curcumin is a natural compound with anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antioxidant effects; however, its clinical use in wound care is restricted by its poor water solubility and low skin absorption. Chronic wounds, often associated with infection and delayed healing, necessitate targeted and effective treatment strategies.

Methods: Transethosomes were developed to improve the topical delivery of curcumin. Their size, structure, and stability were assessed using standard techniques, including dynamic light scattering and electron microscopy. Drug distribution in skin layers was measured through *ex vivo* studies, and FTIR analysis was used to evaluate barrier disruption. Antibacterial activity and cytotoxicity were evaluated *in vitro*, and wound healing was assessed using an *in vitro* scratch assay.

Results: The optimized formulation had a size of 115.8 ± 4.9 nm, low polydispersity index (0.127 ± 0.022), and nearly complete drug loading (99.7%). Skin deposition of curcumin was significantly higher than that in the control ($p < 0.05$) across all layers, with minimal systemic absorption. FTIR confirmed lipid disruption in the stratum corneum. Antimicrobial testing showed preserved activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*. Importantly, the formulation was less toxic to healthy cells (IC_{50} : 12.76 μ g/mL vs. 6.2 μ g/mL for the free drug). Wound healing assays showed 25% faster closure, reaching full repair in 72 hours. These biological endpoints confirmed that enhanced skin deposition was accompanied by improved therapeutic performance.

Conclusion: Transethosomes improved curcumin skin delivery, reduced its cytotoxicity, and accelerated wound healing *in vitro*. This formulation offers a promising strategy for skin-targeted drug delivery, especially in chronic wound care, and supports further testing in advanced wound models in the future.

Keywords

Transethosomes, Curcumin, wound healing, topical delivery, Nanomedicine, skin penetration, antibacterial activity

Introduction

Chronic wounds are a major global health problem, affecting approximately 1% to 2% of the population in developed countries and placing a substantial economic burden

on healthcare systems worldwide (Sen 2019; Sharma et al. 2024). These non-healing wounds are associated with chronic inflammation in the wound bed, impaired cellular proliferation, and excessive proteolytic activity, often compounded by bacterial colonization, which further impedes

healing (Schilrreff and Alexiev 2022). In recent years, significant progress has been made in wound care technology. However, chronic wound management remains challenging, highlighting the need for innovative therapeutic approaches that address the increasingly recognized complexities of impaired healing pathophysiology (Wang et al. 2024).

Curcumin (*diferuloylmethane*), the major bioactive component of turmeric (*Curcuma longa*), has gained prominence as a potential therapeutic agent for wound-healing applications because of its pleiotropic pharmacological properties (Akbik et al. 2014; Sharifi-Rad et al. 2020). Curcumin has been widely studied and shown to influence multiple steps in wound healing, including NF- κ B-mediated anti-inflammatory effects, antioxidant activity via free radical scavenging, antimicrobial effects against wound pathogens, and stimulation of cell migration and proliferation through TGF- β activation (Srivastava et al. 2011; Peng et al. 2021). Collectively, these mechanisms make curcumin a promising agent for managing the multifaceted pathophysiology of chronic wounds.

However, curcumin's therapeutic potential is substantially limited by its inherent physicochemical properties, as it is poorly soluble in aqueous media ($<0.1 \mu\text{g/ml}$), rapidly metabolized, and exhibits low systemic bioavailability (Fernández-Moriano et al. 2019). In addition, for topical wound applications, these drawbacks are exacerbated by the poor penetration of curcumin into the skin owing to the hydrophobic nature and highly protective barrier function of the stratum corneum, which limits the permeation of molecules (Supe and Takudage 2021). Traditional curcumin formulations fail to transport therapeutically active doses to target wound tissues, highlighting the need for sophisticated delivery systems to overcome these shortcomings (Zhao et al. 2024).

Nanocarriers, as drug delivery platforms, have the potential to enhance skin permeability, optimize release kinetics, and improve the stability of bioactive materials for dermal and transdermal treatments (Tiwari et al. 2022). Vesicular systems based on phospholipids have attracted considerable interest because of their biocompatibility, versatility, and structural similarity to biological membranes (Mazzotta et al. 2024). However, conventional liposomes exhibit inadequate penetration through the stratum corneum owing to their rigid bilayer structure and comparatively large size, necessitating the development of second-generation vesicular systems with enhanced skin-penetration capabilities (Ghasemiyeh and Mohammedi-Samani 2020; Nsairat et al. 2022).

Transethosomes are a new class of elastic vesicular systems that combine the permeation-enhancing properties of transfersomes (deformable vesicles) and ethosomes (ethanol-based vesicular carriers), resulting in vesicles with enhanced skin penetration (Raj et al. 2023; Rezigue et al. 2025). These hybrid vesicles incorporate edge activators (non-ionic surfactants) and high ethanol content ($<45\%v/v$) within a phospholipid matrix, creating flexible, low-viscosity vesicles that enhance trans-epidermal permeation (Song et al. 2012; Ascenso et al. 2015). Ethanol

plays a dual role in this system by fluidizing intercellular lipid bilayers in the stratum corneum and enhancing vesicular deformability and drug solubility within the system (Horita et al. 2015).

Transethosomes exhibit superior drug penetration properties compared to liposomes, transfersomes, and ethosomes, as supported by previous findings, further supporting the enhanced permeation capabilities of transethosome delivery (Chowdary et al. 2023; Seenivasan et al. 2025). The use of transethosomes for curcumin delivery offers a novel approach to overcome the limitations of conventional formulations and enhance the therapeutic effects of natural drugs for wound healing.

In the literature, a curcumin transethosomal gel was prepared using Lipoid S100 and Isopropyl Myristate for the transdermal delivery of curcumin to treat psoriasis. However, the levels of IL-17 and IL-23 estimated from psoriatic tissues did not support the in vivo results of this study (Rathod and Pawar 2024). In another study, the physical characteristics of curcumin-loaded transethosomes prepared using Span 60 as a surfactant were evaluated; however, the topical or transdermal permeation in vitro using skin models and in vitro activity of the prepared transethosome were not assessed (Amalia et al. 2021). Recently, curcumin transethosomes were prepared using D- α -tocopherol acid polyethylene glycol succinate as an edge activator for the transdermal delivery of curcumin, which showed improved anti-inflammatory effects on inflammatory swelling in a mouse ear-swelling model (Guo et al. 2025). However, the topical delivery of curcumin-loaded transethosomes and their skin deposition have not been investigated, particularly for wound healing and antimicrobial effects. This justifies the need for the present study.

This study aimed to develop and assess curcumin-loaded transethosomes as a novel topical drug delivery system to improve wound healing. This study investigated the role of transethosomal vesicles in enhancing the skin delivery of curcumin and evaluated whether this approach improves curcumin permeation, stability, and therapeutic effects compared to free curcumin, while ensuring favorable safety and tolerability. By combining physicochemical characterization, skin penetration studies, antimicrobial testing, and wound healing assays, this study highlights the potential of curcumin-loaded transethosomes for chronic wound care, a field that remains underserved despite the clear clinical need.

Materials and methods

Materials

Curcumin was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. Soybean phosphatidylcholine (SPC) (phospholipon 90 G, purity $> 94\%$) was generously provided by Lipoid GmbH (Ludwigshafen, Germany). Tween 80 (polyoxyethylene sorbitan monooleate) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. All other reagents were of HPLC or analytical grade and used as received.

Preparation of curcumin-loaded transethosome formulation

The thin-film hydration method was employed to create curcumin-loaded transethosomes (Visht et al. 2014). In this procedure, curcumin, phospholipids, and surfactants were dissolved in an organic solvent, specifically a 1:1 blend of chloroform and methanol in a round-bottomed flask. The organic phase was vacuum-evaporated at 40 °C using a rotary evaporator (Heidolph Rotary Evaporator, Germany) until a thin lipid film was formed on the inner surface of the flask. The dry lipid film was then hydrated with a 30% (v/v) ethanol solution. After hydration, the vesicles were allowed to expand at room temperature and sonicated using a probe sonicator (Sonics VibraCell, 20 kHz, 50% energy output). The resulting transethosomes were stored at 5 ± 3 °C until further use. Table 1 presents the composition of the optimal transethosomal formulation obtained using this method. For the control experiments, a drug-free transethosome formulation was prepared using the same components and procedures as described above.

Table 1. The components of the transethosomal formulation.

Component	% (W/V)
Curcumin	0.02
Soybean phosphatidylcholine	4
Tween 80	1
Hydration medium	30 % (ethanol/water)

Measurement of vesicular size, Polydispersity Index (PDI), and zeta potential

Dynamic light scattering was performed using a Malvern NanoZS (Malvern Instruments Ltd., UK) to determine the mean vesicular size, polydispersity index (PDI), and zeta potential of the freshly prepared transethosomes at ambient temperature. All measurements were performed in triplicates.

pH measurements

The pH of the transethosome dispersions was measured at room temperature using a Bante 920 benchtop pH meter (Bante Instruments, China). Measurements were performed in triplicate, and the values are presented as the mean ± standard deviation (SD). All readings were obtained under ambient laboratory conditions following standard operating procedures to ensure consistency.

Encapsulation efficiency determination

The encapsulation efficiency (EE) of the liposomal formulation was assessed using ultrafiltration. A volume of curcumin-loaded transethosomes (0.5 ml) was introduced into a centrifugal filter unit (Amicron Ultra -10 K, Merck Millipore, Tullagreen, Carrigtwohill) and centrifuged for 2 h at 6000 rpm and 4 °C. The unencapsulated drug was quantified in the supernatant using high-performance liq-

uid chromatography (HPLC). EE values were calculated as the mean ± standard deviation (SD) of three independent experiments for each group. The EE of curcumin in the transethosomes was calculated using the following equation: (1) (Zhang et al. 2012).

$$EE(\%) = \frac{(\text{curcT} - \text{curcF})}{\text{curcT}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where:

Curc_T represents the total amount of curcumin in the sample.

Curc_F represents the amount of unencapsulated curcumin.

All experiments were performed in triplicates.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) analysis

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM; JEM-1010, JEOL, Japan) was used to perform structural analysis of the curcumin transethosomal formulation. The specimens were placed on carbon-coated copper grids and stained with 1% aqueous uranyl acetate to enhance the contrast. The microscope was operated at an acceleration voltage of 80 kV, with magnification levels ranging from 10,000 to 100,000.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) analysis

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was performed using a Mettler Toledo DSC 1 STARe System to assess the thermal behavior of pure curcumin, curcumin-loaded transethosomes, and unloaded transethosomes. Each sample (4 mg) was placed in a standard aluminum pan with a crimped lid to maintain airtight conditions. The samples were heated at a steady rate of 10 °C/min in the temperature range of 25–300 °C. An empty aluminum pan was used as a reference. The thermograms obtained were analyzed to evaluate the thermal characteristics of the samples, including any peak changes that might indicate curcumin entrapment or interactions, including curcumin entrapment within the transethosomal matrix, as indicated by shifts or disappearance of characteristic melting peaks.

Stability evaluation

Transethosomes were stored under refrigerated conditions at 4 ± 2 °C for three months to assess their physical stability. At predetermined intervals (0, 1, 2, and 3 months), vesicle size, polydispersity index (PDI), and zeta potential were measured using the methodologies described in “Measurement of vesicular size, polydispersity index (PDI)”, and zeta potential. To ensure reliability, each measurement was conducted in triplicate, and the results were reported as mean values with their respective standard deviations (SD).

Human skin permeation and deposition experiments

The preparation of the Skin

Full-thickness human skin obtained from cosmetic surgical procedures was used to study skin permeation and deposition. Subcutaneous adipose tissue was excised using a scalpel after thoroughly cleansing the skin. Subsequently, the skin samples were rinsed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) at pH 7.4 to eliminate any remaining impurities and to maintain tissue quality. Subsequently, the skin samples were stored at -20 ± 2 °C in aluminum foil for further use.

Ex-vivo skin permeation studies

After being divided into suitable sections, the human skin was equilibrated with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) at a pH of 7.4. For the skin permeation experiments, Franz diffusion cells (Permeagear V6A Stirrer, Hellertown, PA, USA; diffusion area 1.23 cm² and recipient volume 14 ml) were used. Skin samples with the stratum corneum facing upward were placed on Franz cells filled with PBS at pH 7.4.

The skin surface was maintained at a constant temperature of 32 °C using a temperature-controlled circulating water bath. The receptor phase was continuously agitated using a Teflon-coated magnetic stir bar rotating at 200 rpm. Subsequently, 1 mL of either the curcumin-loaded transethosomal formulation or curcumin solution in sesame oil (control) was topically applied to the epidermal surface. After a 24-hour incubation period, receptor fluid samples were collected and analyzed for curcumin content using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC).

Ex-vivo skin deposition studies

Skin samples were removed after 24 h, and any remaining formulations were removed by cleansing the skin surface three times with cotton soaked in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). The tape-stripping method was used to separate the stratum corneum layer (Van der Molen et al. 1997), and the epidermis and dermis layers were separated using forceps (Ojeh et al. 2001; Poumay et al. 2004). Twenty Scotch Book Tape strips (1.5 × 1.5 cm, 3 M, St. Paul, MN, USA) were used for tape stripping. The other skin layers, represented by the viable epidermis and dermis, were minced. Absolute methanol was then added to extract curcumin from each layer (tape, epidermis, and dermis). The samples were sonicated for 30 min and then shaken for 4 h in an Orbi-Shaker (Benchmark, Atkinson, USA) at room temperature.

The drug content in the tapes and skin extracts was measured using HPLC analysis after filtration through 0.45 µm filters. The formulation and control were tested in triplicate.

HPLC analysis conditions

High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) was used to measure the encapsulation efficiency (EE) of cur-

cumin and for *ex vivo* permeation and penetration assessments. Chromatographic separation was achieved using a mobile phase composed of acetonitrile and 0.1% orthophosphoric acid in a 50:50 ratio, which was eluted isocratically at a flow rate of 1 mL/min using a Shimadzu LC-20A 2030 HPLC system (Kyoto, Japan). The analysis was performed using a Kromasil C18 column (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5µm, Sweden) with the column oven set to 25 °C (Sivaranjani et al. 2021). UV detection was performed at 430 nm. The sample injection volume was 20 µL. Under these conditions, curcumin was eluted with a retention time of approximately 7 min. A calibration curve was established using curcumin standards ranging from 0.01 to 10 µg/mL, yielding a linear response with a correlation coefficient (R^2) of 0.999. All measurements were performed in triplicates to ensure analytical precision and reproducibility.

ATR-FTIR spectroscopy analysis

ATR-FTIR spectroscopy was used to investigate the effects of curcumin-loaded and unloaded transethosome formulations and drug solutions on human skin. The *ex vivo* skin penetration experiment, as detailed in “Human skin permeation and deposition experiments”, was performed over a 24-hour duration. The skin samples were then removed from the Franz diffusion cells and cleaned following the previously described procedure. Subsequently, the stratum corneum was aligned with the internal reflection element, a ZnSe crystal featuring a 45° trapezoidal cut, of a Shimadzu IRAffinity-1S FT-IR Spectrometer (Kyoto, Japan). To ensure uniform contact between the crystal and skin samples, consistent pressure was applied. To standardize the analysis, a skin blank was initially analyzed. ATR-FTIR spectra were attained with a spectral resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ within the frequency range of 4000–650 cm⁻¹. The absorbances of the C–H symmetric and asymmetric stretching bands at 2850 and 2920 cm⁻¹, respectively, were investigated to detect any shifts in their frequencies. Any shift to higher frequencies results from the interaction between the stratum corneum and drug-loaded or unloaded formulations, which is related to the disruption of the conformational arrangement of intercellular lipids in the stratum corneum.

Antimicrobial activity assessment

The antibacterial efficacy of the curcumin transethosomal formulation against gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* was evaluated *in vitro*. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) values were determined for curcumin-loaded transethosomes, unloaded transethosomes (blank vesicles), and free curcumin solution. The analysis was performed according to standard broth microdilution procedures, with results reported as the lowest concentration at which no visible bacterial growth (minimum inhibitory concentration, MIC) and complete bacterial eradication (minimum bactericidal concentration, MBC) were observed.

Inoculum preparation (Colony suspension method)

A disc of *S. aureus* ATCC 25923 was cultivated in 100 mL of tryptic soy broth at $37\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1$ for 24 h. A small amount of this broth was then transferred and streaked onto a suitable non-selective medium, specifically tryptic soy agar, and incubated at the same temperature to create a fresh culture agar plate aged 18–24 hours. To prepare a sterile saline solution, 3–4 colonies from the organism plate were added. The turbidity of the suspension was adjusted to align with a 0.5 McFarland standard using the Densi-CHEK optical equipment. This adjustment produced a suspension with approximately $1\text{--}2 \times 10^8$ CFU/mL. To create a 20 ml inoculum with 1×10^6 CFU/ml, 200 μL of the prepared suspension was diluted 1:100 with 19.8 ml of sterile Mueller-Hinton Broth (MHB).

Broth microdilution method

A total of 100 μL of each sample, either the drug formulation or control, was added to the first well of a 12-well plate without dilution. Subsequently, 50 μL of Mueller-Hinton broth (MHB) was added to the remaining wells. Subsequently, to establish a series of dilutions, 50 μL was transferred from the first well to the next (which was already filled with 1.0 ml MHB), resulting in a 1:2 dilution. This process was repeated using new tips for each transfer to create nine dilutions for every sample.

Each well received 50 μL of the prepared inoculum, resulting in a final concentration of 5.0×10^5 CFU/mL, which fell within the advised range of $2\text{--}8 \times 10^5$ CFU/mL. An additional 50 μL of each suspension was externally diluted and cultured to confirm the inoculum density. Each sample plate contained two wells: a growth control well with inoculated broth but no sample and a negative control well with broth and no bacteria or sample. The plates were then incubated for 24 ± 2 h at 37 ± 1 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Additionally, a loopful of MIC and higher-concentration wells was streaked over Tryptic Soy Agar (TSA) plates to determine the Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC). The plates were incubated for 24 ± 2 h at 37 ± 1 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The plates were examined for bacterial growth against a dark backdrop after incubation. Turbid growth in all growth control wells and clear negative control wells verified the validity of the test. The inoculum density culture findings confirmed that the investigated organisms had a concentration of $4\text{--}6 \times 10^5$ CFU. Visual inspection was used to determine the MIC and MBC values for each experiment, which was performed in triplicate.

In vitro Cytotoxicity assay

A Sulforhodamine B (SRB) colorimetric assay was used to evaluate cell viability (Skehan et al. 1990; Allam et al. 2018). The human skin fibroblast cell line was cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) in a humidified environment at $37\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ with 5% (v/v) carbon dioxide (CO_2) concentration. The medium was enriched with

100 mg/mL of streptomycin, 100 units/mL of penicillin, and 10% heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS).

In 96-well plates, 100 μL aliquots of cell suspension containing 5×10^3 cells were incubated for 24 h in complete medium. Subsequently, another 100 μL aliquot of medium containing curcumin-loaded transthesomes and free curcumin (0.02 % w/v hydroethanolic solution with 30 % ethanol) at varying concentrations (0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) was introduced to the cells.

After a 72-hour treatment with the drug formulation or solution, the cells were fixed by replacing the medium with 150 μL of a 10% trichloroacetic acid solution (TCA) and incubating for one hour at $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The TCA solution was then removed, and the cells were rinsed five times with distilled water to remove any unbound dye. A 70 μL aliquot of 0.4% (w/v) SRB solution was added, and the mixture was incubated at room temperature in the dark for 10 min. After three washes with 1% acetic acid, the plates were air-dried overnight at room temperature. The protein-bound SRB stain was dissolved using 150 μL of trisaminomethane base solution TRIS (10 mM), and the absorbance was measured at 540 nm using an Infinite F50 microplate reader (TECAN, Switzerland).

In vitro wound healing assay/ In vitro scratch wound closure assay

The migration of human skin fibroblast HSF cells was investigated using a scratch wound closure assay (Jonkman et al. 2014; Main et al. 2020). A humidified 5% (v/v) CO_2 environment was used to maintain the HSF cell line in DMEM supplemented with 100 units/mL penicillin, 100 mg/mL streptomycin, and 10% heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS) at $37\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

For the scratch wound assay, cells were plated onto a coated 12-well plate at a density of 2×10^5 cells/well. They were then cultured overnight at $37\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ with 5% CO_2 and 5% FBS-DMEM. The confluent monolayer was scratched horizontally the following day, and the plate was carefully cleaned with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). Drug-loaded transthesomes and free drug wells were treated with fresh media containing curcumin transthesomes or free curcumin (hydroethanolic solution with 30% ethanol) at concentrations of 10 and 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ (based on the SRB assay results), and control wells (DMEM media) were refilled with fresh medium.

To track the progress of wound healing, images were captured using an inverted microscope at 0, 24, 48, 72, and 96-hour intervals. During these intervals, the plates were maintained at $37\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in 5% CO_2 . Images were analyzed using the MII Image View software (version 3.7). The gap area in each image was measured at these specific times and compared with the initial gap area at $t = 0$ s. The average distance between the edges of the scratch was calculated using MII Image View software version 3.7 to determine the wound width; as cell migration occurred, the wound width decreased. The results are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation.

Fiji-ImageJ software was used to trace the cell-free area in the images to compute the wound areas. Under normal conditions, the wound area shrinks over time. The mean \pm standard deviation was used to represent the results of the study.

Wound closure percentage: $(A_t = 0\text{hr} - A_t = \Delta h) / A_t = 0\text{h}) \times 100$, where $A_t = 0\text{hr}$ is the average wound area measured at time zero when the scratch is conducted, and $A_t = \Delta h$ is the average wound area recorded h hours later. The results are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (Ahmed et al. 2023).

Statistical analyses

For all statistical analyses, we employed a one-way ANOVA with repeated measurements. The researchers used Prism 7.0 software. (La Jolla, CA, USA). Results were deemed statistically significant when the probability value (p) was less than 0.05.

Results

To evaluate the physicochemical characteristics of the developed transethosomal formulations, critical parameters such as vesicle size, polydispersity index (PDI), zeta potential, pH, and encapsulation efficiency (EE) were assessed. These parameters are essential for predicting the stability, permeation behavior, and skin compatibility of the formulations. The results presented in Table 2 and Fig. 2 reflect the performance of both curcumin-loaded

and curcumin-unloaded transethosomes. An image of the optimized formulation is shown in Fig. 1. The following section outlines the detailed findings and their relevance to the topical delivery of curcumin.

Vesicular size, Polydispersity Index (PDI), zeta potential, pH, and Encapsulation efficiency EE determination

Table 2 and Fig. 2 present the findings for the prepared transethosome formulations, including measurements of vesicular size, polydispersity index, zeta potential, pH, and encapsulation efficiency. The optimized curcumin-loaded transethosomal formulation (Fig. 1) exhibited outstanding nanoscale characteristics, with a mean vesicular size of 115.75 ± 4.88 nm and a narrow size distribution (polydispersity index [PDI]: 0.127 ± 0.0219). These vesicles were uniform in size, which is critical for promoting intercellular pathways and enhancing penetration into the dermis. Due to the high lipophilicity of curcumin, which provides it with a high affinity for the lipid matrix, and the optimized drug-to-phospholipid ratio (1:200), the formulation achieved a high encapsulation efficiency ($99.7 \pm 0.09\%$). The moderately negative zeta potential (-5.74 ± 0.47 mV), along with the steric stabilization properties of Tween 80 (Rocchio et al. 2017) contributed to good colloidal stability. The measured pH (4.63 ± 0.058) fell within the physiological pH range of the skin (4.0–6.0), which is generally recommended for topical formulations.

It is important to note that the reported pH value (4.63 ± 0.058) corresponds to the final vesicular dispersion and not the hydration medium. This acidic shift is attributed to the combined effect of phosphatidylcholine, which mildly acidifies upon hydration in ethanol, and curcumin, whose phenolic groups contribute to proton release in the ethanolic solution (Roy et al. 2016; Nelson et al. 2017; Li et

Figure 1. Image of the optimized formulations: Right: curcumin-loaded transethosome Left: curcumin unloaded transethosome.

Figure 2. Size and size distribution measurements for the optimized curcumin-loaded transethosome formulation.

Table 2. The findings for vesicle size, polydispersity index, zeta potential, pH, and encapsulation efficiency EE of the formulated transethosomes with and without curcumin.

Formulation code	Vesicular size (nm)	PDI	Zeta potential (mV)	pH	Encapsulation efficiency (%)
Curcumin-loaded transethosome	115.75 ± 4.88	0.127 ± 0.0219	-5.74 ± 0.47	4.63 ± 0.058	99.7 ± 0.09
Curcumin-unloaded transethosome	109.027 ± 11.02	0.107 ± 0.048	-7.51 ± 1.236	4.71 ± 0.48	/

al. 2021). These interactions, particularly after sonication and vesicle formation, result in a pH lower than that of the original solvent mixture.

TEM Analysis

Fig. 3 shows images of curcumin-loaded transethosome formulation visualized by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) to understand its morphology. TEM validated the formation of the transethosomal architecture, as TEM imaging revealed well-defined transethosomes with spherical morphology. The dynamic light scattering (DLS) results were consistent with the TEM findings, confirming the vesicles' characteristic smooth surface morphology and uniform size distribution. The absence of vesiculation

or fusion further demonstrated the nanoscale stability of the formulation. These results are consistent with other research findings; TEM analysis of hexatriacontane-loaded transethosomes showed spherical vesicles with a constant size range (Aodah et al. 2023), and paneol-loaded transethosomes showed spherical structures using TEM analysis (Chen et al. 2017).

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) analysis

The DSC thermograms of curcumin-loaded transethosomes, unloaded transethosomes, and curcumin are shown in Fig. 4. The DSC thermogram of curcumin is consistent with that reported in the literature (Sayyar and

Figure 3. TEM images for the prepared curcumin-loaded transethosome formulation.

Figure 4. DSC thermograms for curcumin-loaded transethosome, unloaded transethosome, and curcumin.

Jafarizadeh-Malmiri 2019). DSC thermograms revealed the complete absence of curcumin's characteristic endothermic peak (175–180 °C) in the transethosomal formulation, providing conclusive evidence of its molecular level in lipid dispersion within the lipid bilayers. The absence of crystalline structures clearly indicated that the resulting formulation was amorphous (Mishra et al. 2022), contributing to the increased solubility and bioavailability of curcumin. Furthermore, no additional thermal events were detected, confirming the stability of the formulation and the absence of potential drug-excipient interactions.

Stability studies

After three months of storage at 4 °C, the transethosomal formulation maintained physical stability, exhibiting insignificant changes in vesicle size, PDI, or zeta potential ($p > 0.05$) (Table 3 and Fig. 5). Although the vesicle size increased slightly (from 115.75 ± 4.88 nm to 131.95 ± 0.49 nm), the PDI remained below 0.2 (0.127 ± 0.0219 to 0.144 ± 0.049), and the zeta potential showed minimal variation (-5.74 ± 0.47 mV to -4.81 ± 1.58 mV). The absence of phase separation or precipitation throughout the study period further supports the stability of the formulation, which is critical for pharmaceutical development.

Skin permeation and deposition studies

The deposition of curcumin in the stratum corneum, viable epidermis, and dermis after the application of curcumin transethosomal formulation and the control into human skin for 24 h is shown in Fig. 6. The transethosomal formulation exhibited significantly enhanced skin deposition compared to curcumin solution in all skin strata. Specifically, curcumin deposition in the viable epidermis and dermis layers increased by 116.4% and 86.5%, respectively ($p < 0.05$).

Curcumin was undetectable in the receiver compartment, remaining below the HPLC detection limit, indicating its localization within the different skin layers, where it exerts its effects without systemic absorption.

Figure 5. Outline of stability studies of curcumin-loaded and unloaded transethosomes at 4 °C for three months regarding vesicular size (A), PDI (B), and zeta potential (C). Results are presented as the mean \pm SD; no significant changes were detected in the vesicular size, PDI, or zeta potential ($P > 0.05$).

Table 3. Results of stability studies of curcumin transethosome formulation for three months at 4 °C regarding vesicular size, PDI, and zeta potential. Results are presented as the mean \pm SD.

Formulation	Parameters of evaluation	1 Month	2 Months	3 Months
Curcumin-loaded transethosome	Vesicular size	120.9 ± 1.63	127.0 ± 5.23	131.95 ± 0.49
	PDI	0.139 ± 0.014	0.151 ± 0.008	0.144 ± 0.049
	Zeta potential	-4.65 ± 1.08	-5.51 ± 2.51	-4.81 ± 1.58
Curcumin free transethosome	Vesicular size	118.2 ± 4.05	118.4 ± 5.70	130.77 ± 3.75
	PDI	0.119 ± 0.031	0.110 ± 0.008	0.157 ± 0.022
	Zeta potential	-7.36 ± 2.68	-9.4 ± 2.89	-8.83 ± 0.57

Figure 6. Curcumin deposition was studied in the stratum corneum, epidermis, and dermis layers after tape stripping the stratum corneum and separating the epidermis and dermis layers. The evaluation was performed for the curcumin transethosomal formulation and the drug solution used as a control. * $P < 0.05$.

ATR-FTIR spectroscopy analysis

The effect of the prepared curcumin-loaded transethosome and drug solution on the frequency of the C–H asymmetric and symmetric absorbances is shown in Table 4 and Fig. 7.

Attenuated total reflection Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR) was used to observe the lipid organization in the stratum corneum. Any changes in the conformational arrangement of the functional groups are reflected in the changes in absorbance frequencies. Therefore, changes in intercellular lipids in the stratum corneum

Table 4. Peak shifts in C–H asymmetric and symmetric stretching bands of human skin lipids due to applying curcumin transethosomal formulation and controls.

	Asymmetric C–H stretching (cm^{-1})	Symmetric C–H stretching (cm^{-1})
Untreated skin	2920.21 ± 0.2	2850.79 ± 0.3
Curcumin transethosome	2924.09 ± 0.2	2854.65 ± 0.03
Unloaded transethosome	2924.01 ± 0.02	2852.72 ± 0.3
Drug solution	2922.16 ± 0.1	2850.79 ± 0.4

Figure 7. Peak shifts in C–H asymmetric (a) and symmetric (b) stretching bands of human skin lipids due to applying curcumin transethosomal formulation and controls.

due to the use of permeation enhancement techniques can be predicted (Obata et al. 2010). An increase (blue shift) in the C–H symmetric and asymmetric stretching frequency bands was observed with the curcumin transethosomal formulation and drug-free transethosomes compared to that in the untreated skin.

The application of curcumin transethosomes caused a blue shift in the peak location of the symmetric stretching vibration to $2854.65 \pm 0.03 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, whereas that for the untreated skin was positioned at $2850.79 \pm 0.3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. When curcumin transethosomes were used, the asymmetric stretching vibration changed from $2920.21 \pm 0.2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the untreated skin to $2924.09 \pm 0.2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Antimicrobial effect

Table 5 displays the results of an in vitro test of the antibacterial activity of curcumin-loaded transethosomes against *S. aureus* ATCC 25923. The bactericidal and antibacterial activities of curcumin transethosomes were comparable to those of the free drug (30% ethanol/water). The MIC and MBC values for the drug-free transethosomes and hydroethanolic solution could not be calculated (Table 5).

In vitro cytotoxicity assay

The safety of the curcumin transethosomal formulation was evaluated before performing the in vitro wound healing assays. The SRB colorimetric assay was selected because of its reproducibility and low sensitivity to environmental factors among the different methods used to test in vitro cytotoxicity. This technique is less sensitive to environmental factors and exhibits good reproducibility and linearity (Skehan et al. 1990). The curcumin transethosomal formulation was optimized for topical application to

Table 5. Curcumin transethosome's antibacterial effect against *S. aureus* ATCC 25923 in vitro.

	MIC	MBC
Free Curcumin	50 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	100 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
Curcumin Transethosome	50 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	100 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
Unloaded Transethosome	> 50 %	> 50 %
30 % Ethanol/water	> 50 %	> 50 %

the skin. Therefore, cultured human skin cells were selected as a model to assess skin damage. The obtained IC_{50} values are presented in Table 6 and Fig. 8, respectively.

Table 6. IC_{50} values after SRB colorimetric assay.

	IC_{50} ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
Curcumin Transethosome	12.76
Free Curcumin	6.2

Figure 8. The cell viability results obtained from SRB assay after the treatment of human skin fibroblast cells HSF with curcumin transethosome and free curcumin.

In vitro cytotoxicity assessment showed a significant increase in the IC_{50} value of curcumin-loaded transethosomes (12.76 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) compared to free curcumin (6.2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$), demonstrating reduced cytotoxicity with retained therapeutic efficacy. The approximately two-fold improvement in the safety profile is particularly important for wound-healing applications, as cell viability plays a crucial role in tissue regeneration. This reduction in cytotoxicity is likely attributable to the sustained release behavior of transethosomes, which mitigates concentration-dependent toxicity peaks and protects the cells from excessive exposure.

***In vitro* wound healing assay**

The images of the in vitro wound healing assay after applying curcumin transethosome and free curcumin are presented in Fig. 9, and the results of the measurements of wound width, wound area, and wound closure (as a percentage) over time are presented in Figs 10–12.

In a wound-healing assay, wound closure kinetics were significantly enhanced in curcumin-loaded transethosomal-treated cells compared to those in the control and free curcumin-treated groups. At a concentration of 5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, transethosomes achieved complete wound closure within 72 h, whereas the control required 96 h. Wound closure measurements showed that transethosomes accelerated healing by approximately 25% compared with the control. Notably, while free curcumin (10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) resulted in a similar wound closure rate compared to the transethosomes at the same concentration, this concentration exceeded its IC_{50} (6.2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$), raising concerns regarding cytotoxicity. Thus, the transethosomal formulation uniquely enhances potency while offering an improved safety profile, indicating its potential as an advanced wound-healing therapy.

Discussion

This study successfully demonstrated the efficient formulation and comprehensive characterization of a curcumin-loaded transethosomal formulation as a promising nanocarrier platform for enhanced topical wound-healing applications. Our findings highlight the significant advantages of this formulation over traditional delivery systems.

Stability profile and nanoscale characteristics

The optimized transethosomal formulation exhibited good physicochemical characteristics, with a mean vesicular size of 115.75 ± 4.88 nm and a narrow size distribution (PDI: 0.127 ± 0.0219). This nanoscale dimension provides many advantages for dermal delivery, as vesicles with a zeta potential of approximately ± 30 mV are conventionally considered necessary for electrostatic stabilization. However, recent findings suggest that ethanol-containing vesicular formulations can maintain stability despite lower

Figure 9. Photomicrograph of wound scratch assay of control, curcumin transethosome (at 5 and 10 µg/ml) and free curcumin (at 5 and 10 µg/ml).

Figure 10. Wound width results in mm after wound scratch assay of control, curcumin transethosome (at 5 and 10 µg/ml) and free curcumin (at 5 and 10 µg/ml).

Figure 11. Wound area results in mm² after wound scratch assay of control, curcumin transethosome (at 5 and 10 µg/ml) and free curcumin (at 5 and 10 µg/ml).

Figure 12. Wound closure percentage results after wound scratch assay of control, curcumin transethosome (at 5 and 10 µg/ml) and free curcumin (at 5 and 10 µg/ml).

zeta potential values owing to the combined effects of steric and electrostatic stabilization (Bin Jordan et al. 2023). Our three-month stability study further supported this, demonstrating no significant changes in key parameters.

Strategies to improve permeability in skin

Enhanced delivery was demonstrated by the extensive deposition of curcumin in the skin tissue, with significantly higher skin penetration across all skin layers. Compared with the drug solution, deposition increased by 93.4% in the stratum corneum, 116.4% in the epidermis, and 86.5% in the dermis. Several complementary mechanisms may contribute to this enhanced penetration.

The ethanol content (30% *v/v*) served as a penetration enhancer by disrupting the stratum corneum lipids (Pai-va-Santos et al. 2021), leading to significant blue shifts in the C-H stretching vibrations observed in the ATR-FTIR analysis (2920.21 cm^{-1} to 2924.09 cm^{-1} for asymmetric stretching and 2850.79 cm^{-1} to 2854.65 cm^{-1} for symmetric stretching). These spectral changes indicate increased lipid fluidity and reduced lipid chain ordering, creating transient pathways that enhance permeation (Lachenmeier 2008).

Transethosomes have an elastic structure that allows them to pass through tight junctions without rupture, unlike conventional liposomes, which are prone to rupture. This deformability arises from the synergistic action of edge activators (Tween 80) and ethanol, which reduces the interfacial tension and enhance membrane fluidity (Raj et al. 2023; Munir et al. 2024).

The nanoscale size and uniform size distribution facilitate traversal through the tortuous intercellular pathways of the stratum corneum, as substantiated by TEM analysis, which demonstrated homogeneously sized spherical vesicles.

Notably, the absence of detectable curcumin in the receptor fluid following skin permeation indicates that curcumin remains localized within the skin layers, with no evidence of systemic absorption. This finding is particularly advantageous for wound-healing applications, as localized delivery minimizes systemic side effects while ensuring therapeutic activity at target sites. As the objective of this

study was to enhance the local skin deposition of curcumin rather than systemic absorption, conventional *in vitro* release profiling was not performed. This study emphasized skin permeation and deposition studies using human skin, which offers a more biologically relevant model for evaluating therapeutic localization in topical applications.

Therapeutic efficacy and safety profile

The encapsulation of curcumin maintained its antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* (MIC: 50 µg/ml, MBC: 100 µg/ml), indicating that the transethosomal system preserved the pharmacological properties of curcumin. This is particularly crucial in wound-healing applications, where bacterial contamination can significantly hinder the wound-healing process (Krausz et al. 2015; Hussain et al. 2022).

Perhaps most noteworthy is the two-fold improvement in the safety profile, evidenced by an increase in the IC_{50} value (12.76 µg/ml) compared to that of free curcumin (6.2 µg/ml). This added safety margin addresses a major limitation of curcumin therapy, where cytotoxicity is concentration-dependent and commonly limits the therapeutic window of the pathway (Pancholi et al. 2021). This reduced cytotoxicity is likely due to the sustained release mechanisms of the transethosomes, which prevent concentration-dependent toxicity peaks while maintaining adequate therapeutic concentrations at the target site.

The significantly enhanced wound healing kinetics demonstrated in our *in vitro* scratch assay further reinforces the therapeutic potential of this formulation. Achieving complete wound closure within 72 h compared to 96 h in the control group reflects a 25% faster healing rate, a marked improvement that could yield clinically relevant benefits in wound management. Notably, treatment with transethosomal curcumin at 5 µg/mL promoted complete wound closure, forming a continuous cellular monolayer, likely due to improved bioavailability and efficient targeted delivery. This is particularly significant given that free curcumin achieved similar closure only at 10 µg/ml, a concentration exceeding its toxic IC_{50} value (6.2 µg/ml).

Technologic benefits and clinical consequences

The transethosomal system offers numerous technological advantages for pharmaceutical development. The use of generally recognized as safe (GRAS) excipients, combined with a simple and scalable preparation method, enhances the translational feasibility of this formulation. Moreover, its remarkable stability profile during three months of storage eliminates concerns regarding physical instability, which is commonly observed in nanoparticulate systems (Wu et al. 2011).

The pH of the formulation (4.63 ± 0.059) fell within the physiological range of the skin (4.5–6.0), indicating a low likelihood of irritation upon application of the formulation. Notably, the ability to modulate the release of hydrating and water-based substances optimizes many therapeutic approaches, particularly in wound care, where

a balanced microenvironment is essential for cellular regeneration and tissue repair (Duan et al. 2016).

Clinically, the synergistic advantages of enhanced penetration, an improved safety profile, and accelerated wound healing kinetics position curcumin-loaded transthesomes as a promising advanced therapy for chronic wounds, which often exhibit poor healing outcomes. Additionally, their antibacterial effect against *S. aureus*, a common wound pathogen, offers a significant therapeutic advantage that may reduce the need for concomitant antibiotic therapy.

Limitations and future directions

In addition to the promising results of this study, a few limitations should be addressed. Although in vitro models provide valuable preliminary assessments, they may not fully replicate the microenvironment of chronic wounds, which are characterized by impaired vascularization, persistent inflammation, and altered cellular responses. To improve clinical relevance, future studies should incorporate advanced 3D wound models or ex vivo human skin equivalents to enhance the predictability of their clinical efficacy.

Further validation will be carried out using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) to assess the chemical stability of the formulation at both room temperature and 4 °C, confirming the high stability of curcumin over time and the enhanced efficacy of the formulations. Future studies should explore additional storage conditions, particularly focusing on room temperature stability, to further optimize the effectiveness of the formulation.

Overall, the novel use of curcumin-loaded transthesomes for topical delivery applications has the potential to offer substantial benefits for wound healing while effectively overcoming the major drawbacks of conventional curcumin formulations. This approach provides improved penetration, enhanced stability, and an optimized safety profile compared to conventional methods. The findings of this study are highly encouraging and warrant further investigation to facilitate the development of clinically translatable, advanced wound care products.

Conclusions

These findings suggest that curcumin-loaded transthesomes represent a promising approach for next-generation drug delivery systems for topical applications in wound healing. The optimized formulation exhibited remarkable physicochemical properties, including a nanosize of 115.75 ± 4.88 nm, polydispersity index (PDI) of 0.127 ± 0.0219 , high encapsulation efficiency ($99.7\% \pm 0.09$), and stability over three months. The transthesosomal system significantly enhanced the dermal delivery of curcumin across all skin layers while minimizing systemic absorption, effectively overcoming the major limitations of conventional formulations.

This unique dual mechanism of action relies on ethanol's ability to disrupt the structured organization of the stratum corneum lipids, alongside a second mechanism that provides elastomeric vesicles with deformability. Col-

lectively, these mechanisms enable the rational development of a new generation of elastic drug delivery carriers. The enhanced delivery resulted in substantial therapeutic advantages, including preserved antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, minimized cytotoxicity, a two-fold improvement in safety, and accelerated wound healing kinetics, with 25% faster closure rates than that of the control.

This study makes a substantial contribution to the field of wound healing by establishing curcumin-loaded transthesomes as a promising platform for enhanced wound therapy. This approach effectively addresses the primary challenges associated with curcumin delivery, including poor solubility, low stability, and inadequate penetration, while ensuring an improved safety profile of the delivery system. Further in vivo efficacy studies and subsequent clinical trials are crucial for evaluating the clinical applicability of this formulation in managing chronic wounds.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

Use of commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines: ATTC.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

M.R.: Conceptualization, supervision, writing – original draft. A.A.A.A.: Investigation, validation, formal analysis. W.A.: Experimentation, data analysis. All authors reviewed and edited the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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